

Metal Complexes of Piperidinobenzylurea

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Some six/four-coordinated Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of piperidinobenzylurea, a Mannich base derived from urea, piperidine and benzaldehyde, have been synthesised and screened for their antibacterial activity. The complexes exhibit two types of stoichiometry, viz. M₂L and M.L. A few complexes contained coordinated water molecules. The geometries of the complexes have been proposed.

Studies of metal complexes of the formaldehyde based Mannich bases have been reported in literature¹. However, there is no report on preparation of metal complexes with benzaldehyde based Mannich bases except our own work with *N,N*'-bis(morpholinobenzyl)urea².

The present communication reports the synthesis of piperidinobenzylurea, (H₂N-CO-NH-CH(C₆H₅)-NC₅H₁₀) (PBU) by reacting urea, piperidine and benzaldehyde in 1 : 1 : 1 mole ratio and its complexation characteristics with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} salts.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate a 1 : 2 (M : L) stoichiometry for all the complexes except manganese(II) nitrate, cobalt(II) chloro and bromo complexes which exhibit 1 : 1 ratio (Table I). The complexes are soluble in DMSO, nitrobenzene and dimethylformamide. The molar conductance values of the complexes show them to be non-electrolytes³.

Magnetic properties Majority of the manganese complexes are of high-spin. The high-spin *d*⁵-configuration gives a magnetic moment value of 5.9 B.M. according to spin-only formula. However, magnetic moments of the Mn^{II} complexes lie in the range 5.51–5.61 B.M. Octahedral Co^{II} can exist in two possible spin states: (i) low-spin with a magnetic moment of 1.18 B.M. and (ii) high-spin with a magnetic moment of 4.2–5.2 B.M. The observed magnetic moments of the Co^{II} complexes (4.48–4.72 B.M.) indicate high-spin nature of the complexes. In the Ni^{II} complex with octahedral or slightly tetragonally distorted geometry two unpaired electrons are present. The ground state makes no orbital contribution to the magnetic moment so that these

moments are expected to be not greatly different from the spin-only moment value of 2.83 B.M. In tetrahedral geometries also two unpaired electrons are present but there is considerable orbital contribution to the magnetic moment through the equivalence and degeneracy of the incompletely filled *t*₂ orbitals. So, in these cases, normally the magnetic moment values lie in the range 3.4–4.0 B.M. Based on this, all the nickel(II) complexes can be assigned an octahedral geometry around nickel(II) ion since they show magnetic moments in the range 3.25–3.36 B.M. The μ_{eff} values reported for the complexes are slightly higher than the spin-only value of respective metal ions, indicating the spin-free octahedral environment around the metal ions⁴. Mononuclear Cu^{II} complexes have no effective interactions between the unpaired electrons on different Cu^{II} ions thereby providing a class of Cu^{II} complexes whose magnetic moments are almost temperature-independent falling in the range, 1.75–2.20 B.M. In the Cu^{II} dimeric or polymeric species with anionic bridges the spins of Cu^{II} ions are strongly coupled leading to subnormal magnetic moment values. The experimentally determined magnetic moments of the Cu^{II} complexes lie in the range 1.06–1.31 B.M. suggesting strong coupling between the Cu^{II} ions⁵.

Electronic spectra The electronic spectral data for manganese(II) complexes are provided in Table I. Each complex exhibits one or two weak bands in the range 21560–26340 cm⁻¹ (Table I). All the manganese(II) complexes are pale pink in colour indicating six-coordinated geometry, since in tetrahedral environments, the compounds have a noticeable pale yellow-green colour^{6,7}. In the cobalt(II) chloro complex, the absorption maxima observed at 19420 and a weak band at

TABLE I – SPECTRAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	$\lambda_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	A_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
MnCl ₂ .2PBU	21 560	12.61
Mn(NO ₃) ₂ .PBU.2H ₂ O	25 650	27.76
MnSO ₄ .2PBU	22 680 25 795	11.31
Mn(ClO ₄) ₂ .2PBU	26 340 23 460	9.64
CoCl ₂ .PBU.2H ₂ O	19 420 17 130	8.66
CoBr ₂ .PBU.2H ₂ O	21 235	17.15
CoSO ₄ .2PBU	20 130 16 890	33.47
Co(NO ₃) ₂ .2PBU	15 170	14.84
Co(ClO ₄) ₂ .2PBU	15 060	11.79
NiCl ₂ .2PBU	26 230 16 010	15.93
NiBr ₂ .2PBU	24 480 18 020	31.46
NiSO ₄ .2PBU	26 350 16 870	8.91
Ni(NO ₃) ₂ .2PBU	24 680 16 520	26.74
Ni(ClO ₄) ₂ .2PBU	25 470 15 130	23.76
CuCl ₂ .2PBU	12 120 15 920	18.11
CuSO ₄ .2PBU.2H ₂ O	12 370 12 420sh 27 860	17.86
Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2PBU	16 690 21 491	11.35
Cu(ClO ₄) ₂ .2PBU	17 696 22 425	16.18

17 130 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of cobalt(II) in an octahedral surrounding. These bands seen in the visible region can be assigned to $^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition. The absorption maxima of the bromo and sulphato complexes also indicate the octahedral geometry. The cobalt(II) chloro, bromo and sulphato complexes are pink in colour while the nitrate and perchlorato complexes are blue, exhibiting maxima at 15 170 and 15 060 cm⁻¹ respectively, suggesting a tetrahedral en-

vironment around the Co^{II} ion⁶. The bands of the nickel(II) chloro complex observed at 26 230 and 16 010 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) and $^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions respectively, suggesting a distorted octahedral geometry. The absorption maxima of the other nickel(II) complexes also point to the distorted octahedral geometry. In the case of the copper(II) chloro complex two $d-d$ transitions viz $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ and $d_{xz}, yz \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ are located at 12 120 and 15 920 cm⁻¹. The copper(II) sulphato complex shows bands at 12 420sh, 12 370 and 27 860 cm⁻¹, which are characteristic of distorted octahedral geometry. The copper(II) nitrate and perchlorato complexes show bands around 17 000 and 22 000 cm⁻¹, assigned to a planar CuN₂O₂ environment. The electronic spectra rule out tetrahedral structure for the complexes since tetrahedral copper(II) complexes usually show no $d-d$ bands in the range 10 000–20 000 cm⁻¹.

Infrared spectra – In the infrared spectrum of piperidinobenzylurea the ν_{NH} modes appear at 3 460 (asymmetric) and 3 360 cm⁻¹ (symmetric). The carbonyl and (C–N–C) stretching frequencies of PBU appear at 1 660 and 1 160 cm⁻¹ respectively⁸.

The ir spectra of manganese(II) complexes reveal the bidentate nature of the ligand with carbonyl oxygen and the piperidine ring atoms acting as donor sites. Manganese(II) nitrate complex shows additional bands at 3 480, 835 and 630 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of coordinated water⁹. The (N–O) stretching frequencies of the nitrate complex appear at 1 415 (ν_5), 1 340 (ν_1) and 1 045 (ν_2) cm⁻¹. The ν_5 and ν_1 bands are separated to an extent of 75 cm⁻¹ suggesting the unidentate behaviour of nitrate group⁹. In the cobalt(II) chloro, bromo and sulphato complexes, $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ band appears at 1 630, 1 635 and 1 640 cm⁻¹, while $\nu_{\text{C–N–C}}$ band appears at 1 140, 1 150 and 1 135 cm⁻¹ respectively. These indicate coordination through carbonyl oxygen and piperidine ring nitrogen. The ν_{NH} band of the nitrate and perchlorato complexes appear at 3 290 and 3 280 cm⁻¹ respectively, suggesting N coordination of NH₂ group. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C–N–C}}$ band positions remain unaltered in these complexes. The ir spectra of the chloro and bromo complexes indicate the presence of coordinated water.

All the nickel(II) complexes show negative shifts of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C–N–C}}$ vibrations indicating coordination

through the carbonyl group of the urea moiety and the tertiary ring nitrogen. There are no additional bands in the region 3500 cm^{-1} other than ν_{NH} which points to the absence of any coordinated water molecule. The copper(II) chloro complex exhibits coordination through C=O and C-N-C groups. In the copper(II) sulphato, nitrate and perchlorate complexes the ν_{NH} band appears at 3270 , 3330 and 3290 cm^{-1} respectively, while $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N-C}}$ band positions remain unaltered. This is indicative of N coordination of NH_2 group. The sulphato complex has bands at 3480 , 1610 , 870 and 620 cm^{-1} pointing to the presence of coordinated water molecules. Far-IR spectrum of the copper(II) chloro complex shows bands at 325 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cu-C1}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$. The $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cu-O}}$ bands of copper(II) nitrate complex appear at 327 and 267 cm^{-1} respectively.

Thermal studies The nickel(II) chloro complex was found stable up to 186° and showed a steady weight-loss up to 320° . A strong endothermic DTA peak at 210° may be due to the fusion of the complex. The final weight at 660° was 10% more than the calculated weight for nickel(II) oxide. The copper(II) sulphato complex recorded the first decomposition at $135\text{--}150^\circ$ accompanied by a weak DTA peak at 140° . The weight-loss corresponds to the loss of two coordinated water molecules. A sharp endothermic peak observed at 190° corresponds to the fusion of the complex. The final product was identified as CuO at 700° .

Antibacterial screening All the metal chelates (in DMF) were tested for their antibacterial activity by serial tube dilution technique¹⁰ against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. The highest dilution of the test chelates which inhibited the visual growth of the test organisms was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration. The order of activity for the complexes was found to be $\text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Mn}$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR or G.R. (E. Merck) grade. Organic solvents were purified by standard methods.

Synthesis of PBU Urea dissolved in minimum amount of water, was added piperidine followed by benzaldehyde maintaining a temperature of 10° and stirred. The resulting white crystals were washed with

water and crystallised from methanol, (68.7%), m.p. $159\text{--}61^\circ$.

Synthesis of metal complexes The ligand being insoluble in water, all the complexes were prepared in non-aqueous media. The divalent metal salts of manganese, cobalt, nickel and copper were used as such without dehydrating them, since dehydrated salts are insoluble in alcohol. Manganese(II) complexes were prepared by digesting an alcoholic solution containing the ligand and the metal salt in 1:1 mole ratio for 15 min. It was then concentrated to half of its volume, filtered, washed with ethanol and dried at 100° in an air oven. Cobalt(II) complexes were prepared by similar procedure. Nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes were prepared by mixing the alcoholic solutions of the ligand and the metal salt in 1:1 mole ratio and then refluxing for 1 h. The solid complex was washed with ethanol and dried at 100° .

Metal ions and anions were estimated¹¹ and C, H and N analysed.

Molar conductance was measured using $\sim 10^{-3}\text{ M}$ solutions in DMF on a Systronics 304 conductivity meter at room temperature. Magnetic susceptibility was measured by Gouy method at room temperature. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Jasco UVIDEK-430B spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. Thermal data were obtained using a Shimadzu DT-40 instrument. C, H and N were estimated using a Carlo-Erba 1106 Thomas CH analyser-Coleman N analyser.

References

1. A. SABASHIAN and D. VENKAPPAYYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1990, **67**, 584.
2. G. V. PRABHU, Ph.D. Thesis, Bharathidasan University, 1991.
3. W. I. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 1971, **7**, 81.
4. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.* 1964, **6**, 197. N. S. GILL and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1959, 37. O. SHIMAN and H. B. GRAY, *Inorg. Chem.* 1974, **13**, 1158.
5. E. I. ARSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.* 1969, **23**, 2158. 1971, **25**, 962. S. PADHYE and G. B. KAUFMAN, *Coord. Chem. Rev.* 1985, **63**, 127.
6. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Absorption Spectra and Chemical Bonding in Complexes*, Pergamon, Oxford, 1962.

7. I. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 3rd ed. Wiley-Eastern Ltd. New Delhi, 1976.
8. I. F. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", 2nd ed., Methuen, London, 1958. R. M. SILVERSTEIN, G. C. BASLER and T. C. MORRILL "Spectrophotometric Identification of Organic Compounds" 4th ed., Wiley, New York, 1981.
9. K. NAKAMOTO "Infrared and Raman Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", 3rd ed., Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1978.
10. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", 3rd ed., Butterworth, London, 1970.
11. "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", eds. J. BASSIETI, R. C. DENNIS, G. H. JEFFERY and J. HENDHAM 4th ed., ELBS, Longman, 1986.